

Cobalt-, Nickel- and Copper(II) Complexes of Schiff Bases with N or S Donor Sites

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Condensation of 2-aminothiazole and its derivatives with *vic*-hydroxyaldehydes gives Schiff bases which form complexes of the type ML_2 with bivalent transition metals. The ligand molecule contains both N and S donor sites and coordination through any one atom is possible. The elemental analysis suggests 1 : 2 stoichiometry, magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectral data are in favour of octahedral structure for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes. Infrared spectral data indicate bonding through oxygen atom of the hydroxyl group and a possibility of coordination through nitrogen atom, each of the ligand molecule. Complexes are found to be of nonelectrolytic nature.

Ligand molecules containing heterocyclic nitrogen and sulphur atom are important from structural point of view. In recent years, because of new interesting applications found in the field of pesticides and medicine, the metal complexes with tridentate O, N, N, or O, N, S types of alternative structures have attracted the attention of chemist.

The present study is based on use of new Schiff bases capable of forming O, N, N or O, N, S arrangement with equal ease and attempts have been made to throw light on the possible structures. We report here the preparation of fortyeight new metal complexes using sixteen Schiff bases derived from four amines and four aldehydes. Their identification and structural characteristics are discussed.

R = H, CH₃, OCH₃, Cl
R' = 3-CH₃, 3-Cl, 3,5-dichloro, 5-Br

Results and Discussion

The complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} (Table 1) are crystalline solids, soluble in chloroform, nitrobenzene and benzene, and decompose above 250°. The molecular weights data suggest the

monomeric nature of ML_2 complexes. Very low conductance values of complexes measured in nitrobenzene suggest non-electrolytic nature of the ML_2 complexes.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA OF Co^{II} , Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Sl. no	R	R'	Analysis % · Found / (Calcd)				Metal
			C	H	N	S	
<i>Co^{II} complex:</i>							
1.	H	CH ₃	63.04 (63.27)	4.25 4.03	8.72 8.68	9.80 9.92	9.00 9.13
2.	CH ₃	CH ₃	64.30 (64.19)	4.70 4.45	8.21 8.32	9.43 9.31	8.52 8.75
3.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	61.08 (61.28)	4.21 4.26	7.68 7.94	9.25 9.07	8.17 8.36
4.	Cl	CH ₃	57.14 (57.34)	3.15 3.36	7.59 7.84	8.75 8.96	8.06 8.26
5.	H	Cl	50.85 (50.97)	2.80 2.91	7.98 8.16	9.78 9.32	8.46 8.06
6.	CH ₃	Cl	57.00 (57.14)	3.35 3.25	7.65 7.84	8.75 8.96	8.01 8.26
7.	OCH ₃	Cl	54.52 (54.59)	3.04 3.22	7.32 7.50	8.29 8.57	7.72 7.90
8.	Cl	Cl	50.68 (50.86)	3.20 2.38	7.54 7.41	8.21 8.47	7.80 7.31
9.	H	3,5- Cl ₂	50.57 (50.68)	2.08 2.37	7.12 7.39	8.26 8.44	7.62 7.90
10.	CH ₃	3,5- Cl ₂	51.64 (50.82)	2.57 2.80	6.78 6.96	8.00 8.14	7.26 7.57
11.	OCH ₃	3,5- Cl ₂	49.86 (50.00)	2.39 2.69	6.53 6.70	7.51 7.66	7.02 7.33
12.	Cl	3,5- Cl ₂	46.28 (46.55)	1.70 1.94	6.35 6.60	7.49 7.75	7.01 7.26

Table-1 (Contd.)

13.	Cl	Br	49.03 (49.49)	2.30 2.58	7.01 7.21	8.05 8.25	7.49 7.72
14.	CH ₃	Br	50.42 (50.79)	2.75 2.99	6.74 6.97	7.32 7.69	7.12 7.39
15.	OCH ₃	Br	48.50 (48.71)	2.01 2.28	5.95 6.10	7.45 7.65	7.02 7.16
16.	Cl	Br	45.10 (45.44)	2.00 2.13	6.33 6.62	7.29 7.57	6.89 7.08
<i>Ni^{II} complex :</i>							
1.	H	CH ₃	62.87 (63.27)	4.12 4.03	8.50 8.68	10.13 9.93	9.42 9.13
2.	CH ₃	CH ₃	64.35 (64.19)	4.25 4.01	8.40 8.32	9.54 9.31	8.62 8.75
3.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	61.08 (61.28)	4.20 4.27	7.83 7.94	9.26 9.07	8.11 8.36
4.	Cl	CH ₃	57.53 (57.34)	3.54 3.36	7.60 7.84	8.80 8.96	8.45 8.26
5.	H	Cl	55.80 (55.97)	2.80 2.91	8.30 8.16	9.13 9.32	8.70 8.60
6.	CH ₃	Cl	57.30 (57.14)	3.20 3.36	7.98 7.94	8.86 8.96	8.15 8.26
7.	OCH ₃	Cl	54.50 (54.69)	3.32 3.54	7.30 7.50	8.40 8.57	8.65 7.90
8.	Cl	Cl	51.08 (50.86)	2.18 2.38	7.55 7.41	8.59 8.47	7.70 7.81
9.	H	3,5- Cl ₂	50.44 (50.87)	2.21 2.39	7.15 7.42	8.25 8.48	7.49 7.78
10.	CH ₃	3,5- Cl ₂	51.81 (52.00)	2.49 2.80	6.67 6.97	7.69 7.97	7.08 7.31
11.	OCH ₃	3,5- Cl ₂	50.40 (50.08)	2.35 2.70	6.54 6.87	7.62 7.86	6.89 7.20
12.	Cl	3,5- Cl ₂	46.38 (46.72)	1.72 1.95	6.38 6.64	7.54 7.77	6.80 7.00
13.	Cl	Br	49.30 (49.57)	2.24 2.58	7.01 7.23	8.01 8.28	7.30 7.58
14.	CH ₃	Br	50.55 (50.82)	2.65 2.99	6.98 7.62	7.62 7.97	6.87 7.14
15.	OCH ₃	Br	48.49 (48.88)	2.01 2.28	6.71 7.14	7.14 7.48	6.81 7.03
16.	Cl	Br	45.16 (45.50)	1.95 2.13	6.34 6.64	7.21 7.58	6.74 6.96
<i>Cu^{II} complex :</i>							
1.	H	CH ₃	62.54 (62.76)	3.79 4.00	8.70 8.61	9.59 9.58	9.58 9.43
2.	CH ₃	CH ₃	63.48 (63.71)	3.14 4.42	8.08 8.25	9.15 9.43	9.06 9.41
3.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	60.71 (60.84)	3.00 4.25	7.63 7.88	8.84 9.01	8.84 9.00
4.	Cl	CH ₃	56.60 (56.74)	3.07 3.33	7.68 7.79	8.76 8.90	8.70 8.86
5.	H	Cl	55.25 (55.57)	2.95 2.89	7.84 8.10	8.02 9.26	9.03 9.25
6.	CH ₃	Cl	56.37 (56.74)	3.28 3.33	7.30 7.79	8.72 8.60	8.60 8.88
7.	OCH ₃	Cl	54.50 (54.37)	3.30 3.19	7.24 7.54	8.26 8.52	8.24 8.50

Table-1 (Contd.)

8.	Cl	Cl	50.35 (50.52)	2.21 2.36	7.15 7.36	8.19 8.42	8.17 8.40
9.	H	3,5- Cl ₂	50.29 (50.26)	2.10 2.37	7.11 7.37	8.02 8.23	8.10 8.36
10.	CH ₃	3,5- Cl ₂	51.19 (51.53)	2.58 2.78	6.89 7.07	7.95 8.10	7.87 8.03
11.	OCH ₃	3,5- Cl ₂	50.00 (49.67)	2.37 2.68	6.47 6.83	7.40 7.63	7.30 7.75
12.	Cl	3,5- Cl ₂	46.10 (46.34)	1.71 1.93	6.34 6.75	7.45 7.72	7.34 7.76
13.	H	Br	49.03 (49.27)	2.27 2.56	6.80 7.02	8.01 8.20	7.90 8.15
14.	CH ₃	Br	50.28 (50.53)	2.69 2.97	6.67 6.93	7.72 7.92	7.50 7.86
15.	OCH ₃	Br	48.33 (48.61)	2.01 2.28	6.38 6.67	7.41 7.62	7.29 7.57
16.	Cl	Br	45.40 (45.14)	1.97 2.12	6.30 6.58	7.32 7.52	7.20 7.46

Electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes gave three bands. Koning's method was used to ascertain the correct position of the bands¹. The strong and intense charge transfer band is shown by the complex at ~ 26 000 cm⁻¹. The assignments of the spectral bands are as follows : ⁴T_{2g} ← ⁴T_{1g} (ν₁) (≈ 8 500), ⁴T_{2g} ← ⁴T_{1g} (ν₂) (≈ 18 000) and ⁴T_{1g} ← ⁴T_{1g} (ν₃) (≈ 20 000 cm⁻¹). The magnetic moments of the complexes (4.8–5.2 B.M.) are in confirmation with octahedral structure of cobalt complexes². The Ni^{II} complexes also exhibit three *d-d* transition bands for the transitions : ⁴T_{2g} ← ³A_{2g} (ν₁) (≈ 8 000), ³T_{1g} (F) ← ³A_{2g} (ν₂) (≈ 13 000) and ³T_{1g} (F) ← ³A_{2g} (ν₃) (≈ 22 000 cm⁻¹). The magnetic moments of the complexes (3.0–3.3 B.M.) are in confirmation with octahedral complexes³. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complexes exhibit band at ~ 15 000 cm⁻¹, assigned to ²T_{2g} ← ²E_g transition. A strong charge transfer band observed at ~ 26 000 cm⁻¹ and magnetic moments of 1.9–2.0 B.M. suggest an octahedral geometry⁴.

The infrared spectra of ligands do not show phenolic OH band at ~ 3 100 cm⁻¹ but it is shifted towards lower frequency at ~ 2 800 cm⁻¹, and this is in favour of the intramolecular hydrogen bond formation between hydroxyl hydrogen and nitrogen of the azomethine group as well as with endocyclic nitrogen of thiazole ring⁵. The ligand shows C–H frequencies as per expectation. The infrared spectra of the metal complexes show that

the ligand band at $\sim 2800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ disappears, while the C=O and C=N frequencies of the ligand occur at ~ 1280 and 1630 cm^{-1} respectively, which indicate the shifting to higher frequency at $\sim 1320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and lowering at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These observations are in favour of bonding through oxygen of phenolic group and coordination through nitrogen of azomethine group⁶. The endocyclic C-N frequency should act as a marker of preferential choice between square-planar and octahedral geometry.

The coordination of the nitrogen to the metal atom is expected to reduce the electron density in azomethine group and causes a reduction in the C=N frequency. The relative coordinating affinities are between the sulphur and nitrogen donor atoms in the ligands and metal atom⁷. As proposed by Ahrlund *et al.*⁸ the class (b) behaviour of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and the relative affinities are in favour of N_4O_2 structure (I) rather than $\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ structure.

Experimental

The Schiff bases were prepared by following the reported method⁹. A mixture of one mole each of 4-aryl-2-aminothiazole and substituted-salicylaldehyde (3-methyl/3-chloro/3,5-dichloro/and 5-bromo-salicylaldehyde) dissolved in ethanol, was refluxed on a water-bath for ~ 1 h. The Schiff base thus formed was crystallised from ethanol and dried in a vacuum oven.

Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were prepared by refluxing the Schiff base and metal acetate in 2:1 mole ratio in ethanol for 40–45 min and the resulting crystals were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Elemental C, H, N, S analyses were carried out. Metals were determined by standard procedures¹⁰. Molecular weight was determined by cryoscopic method using benzene as a solvent. Electronic spectra (CHCl_3) were taken on a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer and infrared spectras (KBr) on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. Electrical conductivity of the complexes was measured in nitrobenzene using a Philips PR 9500 conductivity bridge. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method at room temperature, diamagnetic corrections were applied by using Pascal's constants¹¹.

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